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ADKAR MODEL TO MANAGE ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

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Abstract

KSC Beauty Clinic Jember is a family company that is always evolving in their business activities. In the development that occurs from time to time, always there is a change in the organization as well as the company's operating system. Basically, the change is a response of the developments following the change of the way of life and era. Some aspects of the changes in the change is the change in the system of corporate planning. As a service company which has several branches outside the town of Jember, Jember KSC Beauty Clinic is also changing organizational management with the Iconix software implementation system (cloud) in company with the objective of efficiency and effectiveness of corporate management. In this paper we will discuss one Adkar change management model consisting of elements of awareness, desire, knowledge, ability and reinforcement in implementing the Iconix system (cloud) at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember.

Introduction

In an increasingly competitive world, change is an absolute necessity. However, empirical experience shows that efforts to change are not always successful. Therefore, changes that need to be managed properly. Change management is the management of resources to achieve the goals of the organization, in environmental conditions that moves constantly. Change management needs to take lessons from previous experience, running a change process properly and granting roles and responsibilities to all stakeholders in accordance proportions.

All organizations are part of the social system that lives in the midst of society. Society itself has a dynamic nature, always changes and developments. Characteristics of such a society requires the organization to also have dynamic properties. Without dynamics in line with the dynamics of the community, the organization will not survive let alone thrive. This means that a change in an organization is a necessity that can not be avoided. They are constantly have to adapt to the demands and changes in the environment.

The process of adjustment to the environment is one of the major problems facing modern organizations. Unless changes aimed at adapting to the changing environment, the organization considers necessary sometimes deliberately make changes to improve the effectiveness of the achievement of the objectives that have been defined. Because of the nature and objectives of each organization are different from each other, the frequency and levels of occurrence of any changes that are not always the same. Certain organizations more frequent changes, while other organizations are relatively rarely do.

Model changes in the company's own, one of which can be done using the model Adkar change. Adkar which stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement which are five basic elements that drive change.

Implementation Adkar approach in the management of the company does not easily run as expected. This is due to the various obstacles that can cause a failure such as experience or history held beliefs that are not appropriate, excessive fear of change, cost dikeluarkan very large and even there is an interest which is very high for certain groups that are considered only benefit certain parties, KSC Beauty Clinic Jember is a family company that is always evolving in their business activities. In the development that occurs from time to time, always there is a change in the organization as well as the company's operating system. Basically, the change is a response of the developments following the change of the way of life and era. Some aspects of the changes in the change is the change in the system of corporate planning.

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Theoretical basis

A. Change Management

In essence, human life and organisasi always moved and overwhelmed by the changes on an ongoing basis. Changes occur because of environmental and external changes. According to Nasution (2010: 3) The change refers to an occurrence of something that is different from before. Change can also mean doing things in a new way, to follow a new path, merging, reorganizing, or the occurrence of events that are disturbing very significant. Change management is a systematic process of applying the knowledge, tools and resources necessary to affect change in people affected by the process. management changes aimed at providing the necessary business solutions successfully in an organized way and method, through the management of change impact on the people involved.

The approach in the management of change are as follows:

1. Identify objects are affected by changes that may resist change.
2. Tracking source, the type and level of resistance to changes that may be found.
3. Designing an effective strategy for reducing the resistance.

There are several factors that cause changes, including:

- 1) Technological change continues to increase.
- 2) Competition has intensified to become global competition.
- 3) More and more demanding consumers.
- 4) Demographic profile of a country changes.
- 5) Privatization of public-owned businesses continues.
- 6) Shareholders who require the development of corporate value.

B. Adkar Model

Adkar models introduced by Prosci in 2001 after researching more than 700 companies that undergo a large change projects. The explanation of each element Adkar are as follows:

- Awareness, Namely the stage to raise the awareness of employees about the planned changes occur
- Desire, Namely the stage where employees' already started to have a "desire for change" in accordance with the plan
- Knowledge, Which is a stage in which not only the employees understand the purpose of the change and the importance of it to the company but also know how to run it
- Ability, Namely the stage where the employee is expected to have the ability to execute change well
- Reinforcement, Namely the stage where changes had been made to keep dipertahankan and even enhanced.

The benefits of the model can be used Adkar is as follows:

1. Diagnose resistance / refusal of members of the organization
2. Help transition members of the organization through the change process
3. Create a successful plan for personal and professional improvement as changes
4. Develop a change management plan for members of the organization.

Adkar approach is an effort to develop an understanding, the will, the knowledge society's changing for the better with a balanced capability to make changes at the same time trying to maintain what resulted from these changes. A change will go well if the public have the awareness of the need for change, a desire to support and participate in the change process, have knowledge of how to make changes, ability to make changes and provide

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reinforcement for the sustainability of the changes.

Awareness, desire, knowledge, ability and reinforcement (Adkar) a significant impact at every stage of management education program as an effort to change. Management education program begins with the identification of the need to implement the program, program designing, implementing and monitoring and evaluation program.

Previous research

Sherry Finney and Martin Corbett (2007) examines the company's ERP implementation in the UK. The purpose of this study was to explore the critical success factors of ERP implementation, and identify any gaps that may exist. Findings - The most significant finding was the lack of research that focuses on the identification of key stakeholder perspectives. In addition, there seems to be a lot of variance in terms of what is actually covered in change management, one of the most widely cited and little detail the specific implementation tactics.

Shih-Wei Chou a and Yu-Chieh Chang (2008) investigated the factors that affect the implementation of the ERP (enterprise resource planning). This study examines the performance in the ERP post-implementation phase, particularly from the perspective of managerial intervention. In particular, they proposed that the customization and organization mechanisms affect benefits (including increased coordination and task efficiency), which in turn affects the company's overall profits. Enterprise-level surveys used to collect data. Their findings support the hypothesis. Among others: (H1) For companies that have implemented ERP, greater customization associated with an increase greater coordination ERP acquired the company. (H2) or companies that have implemented ERP, greater customization associated with greater task efficiency of the ERP to be paid to the company. (H3) For companies that have implemented ERP, the greater the extent to which OM (Organization Mechanism) is characterized by OM OM strategic and operational, the greater the improvement of coordination. (H4) For companies that have implemented ERP, the greater the extent to which OM is considered characterized by strategic and operational OM OM, the greater will be the efficiency of their duties. (H5) For companies that have implemented ERP, greater improvements in coordination with other sub-units associated with the overall benefits of ERP larger. And (H6) For companies that have implemented ERP, a bigger task in efficiency associated with the overall benefits of ERP as a whole.

Henry A. Hornstein (2013) stated the integration of project management and organizational change management is now a necessity. Project management processes and training a new project manager (Project Manager PM) should consider the impact of organizational changes on the success and failure of implementation of the project. The case requires the project manager to adapt to organizational change management (Organization Change Management/ OCM) is made by the author by reviewing the literature supporting. Additionally, the certification body such as PMI and IPMA PM is highly recommended to include education about OCM's new PM certification process.

Technological and medical progress have accelerated the pace of change in the world of health care dramatically. The new technology, the changing needs of the patient, and economic pressures all contribute to the needs of healthcare organizations to modify practices on an ongoing basis. Improved quality (Quality Improvement / QI) process is currently very important in this effort. To better manage the introduction of the changes through a QI in healthcare organizations, need to focus on the public side is change. Change management is the act or process that is done to smooth the transition of individuals or groups from the current state to the desired state in the future. The author provides an overview of the steps to design and implement QI projects that require change management. Key steps for successful change management including assessing readiness for change, building a sense of urgency, assemble a steering committee, develop an implementation plan, the implementation of a pilot, deploy changes, and delaying a change in the organization. Adoption of change management practices increase the chances of success because the focus is placed on the people in the organization who make things happen. The essence of this statement is the change management for an effective quality improvement (Prathibha Varkey, MBBS, MPH, MHPE, and Kayla Antonio, 2010) Adoption of change management practices increase the chances of success because the focus is placed on the people in the organization who make things happen. The essence of this statement is the change management for an effective

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Jong-Hun Park, Hyun-Ju Suh, and Hee-Dong Yang (2005) examined the absorption capacity perceived by individual users in the performance of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP): The Case for Korean companies, find three components are considered to understand, assimilate, and implementing ERP knowledge. They found that the user's ability to assimilate and apply knowledge has a direct and indirect effect on its value. The ability of users to understand the knowledge of ERP found to affect their performance by assimilating and applying knowledge. They also found that support the organization moderated the relationship between absorption capacity and performance.

Sylvia Tamsir, Fadil Amirudin and Abdul Rahman (2008) examines the management information system consumer goods distributor good at. Distrindo Multijaya. They found the Management Information System is an information system to collect, process data and provide information to all levels of management in an organization that values its information later can be helpful in making a decision. The purpose of this paper is to design a management information system with object-oriented development at PT Distrindo Multijaya. The method used to design this system is the method of the Rational Unified Process (RUP) with the development model of the Unified Model Language (UML). There are several phases in the RUP method which includes inception, elaboration, construction, and transition. Design and Implementation of Management Information Systems PT Distrindo Multijaya do with the programming language Visual Basic 2008 and SQL Server 2005 database system is expected to assist the management of PT Distrindo Multijaya in supporting various business activities by providing information such as inventory reports, purchase and sale detail.

Same thing on the research Fendi, Maryanto, and Suwirno Mawlan (2007) with a study entitled Analysis and Design of Information Systems Spare Parts Sales Management Using Object Oriented methodology at CV. Putra Gemilang, found that manajemen Information System is an application of information systems within the organization to support the information needed by all levels of management. The aim of this thesis was to design padaCV Management Information System. Putra Gemilang. The method used is object-oriented methods. The design and implementation will be carried out with VB.Net programming languages and database SQL Server 2005. The system is expected to help the director at CV Putra Gemilang in the planning and control by providing useful information.

Sigit Warisman, Pack M Wahyu Hidayat, and Mardiani S.SI, MTI (2010) suggested the data warehouse is a means used to hold large amounts of data, to build a data warehouse tools microsoft needed a SQL server 2008 and Microsoft SQL business intelligence development. By using the tools microsoft SQL server 2008 and Microsoft SQL business intelligence development can be built a data warehouse to collect dataobat students pharmaceuticals include, time, insurance, pharmacy, medicine, and patients were entered into a Ms. Excel then the result of Ms. Excel microsoft entered into the database SQL server 2008, after the data is entered into the database then the data is loaded into a Microsoft SQL business intelligence development for analysis.

Review of the literature about ERP conducted by Young Moon (2007) concluded the majority of articles that attempt to capture the difference between the different culture or country is limited to one or two of them. Large-scale, simultaneous survey studies can yield useful insights into this issue. The concept of ERP seems to be growing and growing. It would be useful to investigate topics such as how companies using ERP systems to understand these trends, how they would handle the change, tools, methodologies, models what is useful in their expansion efforts, etc.

Young Hoon Kwak, Jane Park, Boo Young Chung, and Saumyendu Ghosh (2011) examined the understanding of end user acceptance of ERP in Project-Based Sector. This study aims to provide an alternative reception Companies Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP). Despite the extensive literature, there is still an empirical question to investigate the implementation of ERP systems from the perspective of end users as well as from

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different organizational contexts. To address this issue, we assign a project-based sector as the population of our interest and try to understand how the project management practices are intertwined with cognitive perception of the end user, and ultimately, with the intention of their behavior using the ERP system. Thus, this study combines the best practices of ERP system implementation project, internal support, external support (consultant), and selection functionality, expanded into the technology acceptance model (Technology Acceptance Model / TAM), which includes construction of trust and build a social environment (subjective norm). Empirical analysis shows that managerial practices and socio-economic factors were significantly associated with the original TAM variables in the context of the ERP system. One interesting finding is negative. This study will also benefit project-based sector by offering valuable insights into managerial which allows them to appreciate and improve the acceptance and utilization of ERP system end users. expanded into the technology acceptance model (Technology Acceptance Model / TAM), which includes construction of trust and build a social environment (subjective norm). Empirical analysis shows that managerial practices and socio-economic factors were significantly associated with the original TAM variables in the context of the ERP system. One interesting finding is negative. This study will also benefit project-based sector by offering valuable insights into managerial which allows them to appreciate and improve the acceptance and utilization of ERP system end users. expanded into the technology acceptance model (Technology Acceptance Model / TAM), which includes construction of trust and build a social environment (subjective norm). Empirical analysis shows that managerial practices and socio-economic factors were significantly associated with the original TAM variables in the context of the ERP system. One interesting finding is negative. This study will also benefit project-based sector by offering valuable insights into managerial which allows them to appreciate and improve the acceptance and utilization of ERP system end users.

Profile KSC Beauty Clinique Jember

KSC Beauty Clinic Jember has several branches outside Jember. Clinic Center and 1 branch in Jember city, one in Balikpapan and one KSC beauty care salon in Malang. Distance apart is one of the problems of corporate consolidation and corporate resource planning. But it does not make the reason for KSC Beauty Clinic to continue to develop.

Changes Information Systems Company KSC Beauty clinique Jember

System KSC changed from initially using IPOS with the classic problem still there are manual and doctors could not take part in the system because of restrictions the options menu application (work files tricky) to change or switch to the system of pharmacy clinic / web base system: physicians can contribute in workmanship file but still not too maximal still no manual workmanship.

Due consideration for more efficient job management and management's desire to reduce the use of paper documents (paperless) in their business activities, the system turns the clinic pharmacy receipts Iconix software system (cloud) that offers several advantages:

- a. Almost no more manual facilitates the pharmacies and clinics for operational work files
- b. Facilitate branch to collaborate interact and sinkroniksasi between branches.

KSC Adkar Analysis Research Methodology

Adkar approach is an effort to develop an understanding, the will, the knowledge society's changing for the better with a balanced capability to make changes at the same time trying to maintain what resulted from these changes. A change will go well if the public have the awareness of the need for change, a desire to support and participate in the change process, have knowledge of how to make changes, ability to make changes and provide reinforcement for the sustainability of the changes.

a. Phase Data and Information

In this process of data collection and information from the literature. So that the input of this process is the problem and the literature regarding the implementation of Iconix System and organizations that serve the KSC Beauty Clinic research Jember. The outcome of this process is the data and information regarding the Iconix System implementation, case studies from the KSC Beauty Clinic Jember and activities in organizational change management activities Adkar models.

b. Analysis Phase Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement Model Adkar

From the results of the mapping shows that the preparation phase implementation program Iconix System there are elements of awareness. In the model Adkar, in the awareness phase will also involve other elements of the desire and knowledge. These three elements are interrelated and move flexibly, which means that if there is an element that is lacking, it can be returned to the previous element for improvement.

c. Identification Phase Change Management Activities

Organizations in Iconix System Implementation at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember After obtaining the forms of activity to build awareness, desire and knowledge based on previous studies, the next step is to identify activities that allow to be done at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember. Then, a list of those activities adapted to the present state of the KSC Beauty Clinic Jember yang obtained from observations (observation) in the workplace and interview with the Head of the IT Division.

The result of the process is a list of organizational change management activities at Iconix System implementation at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember. Then from the list made a coherent priority based on the level of effectiveness.

d. Stage Validating Results

The validation process is done through interviews and discussions with the head of the IT division at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember relevant results. Once validated, then the final result of this phase is a list of organizational change management activities at Iconix System implementation at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember are valid. Iconix Implementation System contains at KSC Beauty Clinic Jember Using Adkar Model.

Iconix implementation Analysis System model Adkar

a. Awareness

At the awareness stage more emphasis on the activity of the activity to establish communication and build awareness to the employees. Some of the subject matter or activities carried out through the following activities:

- Briefed on changes in board meeting

In this meeting, the owner of KSC as president can remind their Iconix System implementation and provide guidance to all branch heads about their business process changes in order to prepare for new business processes at the same time other matters relating to the business process changes.

- Individual changes in the meeting discussion

Changes that may occur the first implementation Iconix System, in accordance with the new responsibilities assigned to each employee. Therefore, there needs to a meeting attended by all branches in order KSC Beauty Clinic recalled that Iconix System implementation will be carried out and will have an impact on employees.

- Iconix discussion Insertion System at branch meetings

Head of the branch in the activities of its regular meeting, gave an insight into Iconix System to each employee so that each employee in the most individual level understand the changes caused by the implementation of Iconix System.

- Held Socialization of Iconix System

Having previously existing System Iconix discussion in the meeting, the management company conducted the relevant authorized organizational changes related to the implementation of Iconix System. Socialization is expected to provide full consciousness urgensi changeovers at KSC Beauty Clinic by implementing the Iconix System.

- Enabling and reuse or group online forum
- Creating a slide presentation and video about Iconix System

For the sake of understanding of the implementation of Iconix System management can make a slide presentation with a video about the benefits of the implementation of Iconix System. Presentations and videos have also been bundled performance module provided by Iconix management system for its clients. Distribution itself biased using forums and groups online or via email each - each employee.

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b. Desire

Management of organizational changes made to cultivate the desire and prevent their refusal of employees to change. In creating desire, can be realized through the following activities:

- Personal approach

Every employee must have an impact with the implementation of Iconix System. Here the head of the branch provides personal guidance related to changes in the organization.

- Listen to opinions of employees

Opinion is ejected from the employees, should be used as material for policy management. The opinion is expected to be a benchmark for the extent of the interest of employees will be changes

- Directly address the benefits and changes for the better on their implementation of Iconix System through socialization

Besides approaching personnel, management also demonstrates the benefits of the implementation of Iconix System for a change, then the benefits it would have a positive influence on each employee. Thus employees will be more confident and the spirit of the changes that occur.

- Make a commitment

Changes that occur with implementation expected senantia Iconix System is maintained and every employee and management are committed to make changes due to the implementation Iconix System.

c. Knowledge

At this stage of knowledge refers to the knowledge and capabilities to employees regarding the implementation of the System Iconix can be realized through the following activities:

- Education held on Iconix System

Iconix software management system training regularly and gradually ranging from basic training in the use of software Iconix System to adjust to the Iconix software update System

- Conducting computer training routine

Conducted regular training to make employees use System Iconix familiar with the system. However, this training can also be done in the daily activities – day

- Provides modules and related materials Iconix System

Modules are usually readily available and can be downloaded at the website Iconix System. The module cover is printed or shared with KSC to be distributed to employees as a guide in the application Iconix System

- Providing access to information related to Iconix System

Access to information about Iconix System can be accessed at the website Iconix System.

d. Ability

Ability is the ability to apply knowledge be realized or the implementation of changes. Ability achieved if a person has the ability to implement changes to the specified level of performance.

- The supervisors in daily practice, so as to create a comfortable environment for learning new skills and habits.

- Providing access to subject matter experts, in order to reduce the knowledge gap and obtain a demonstration one by one.

- Implement a performance monitoring program that measurable progress as the expected result of the change.

- Providing hands-on exercises during training so that employees can put into practice what they have learned.

e. Reinforcement

Reinforcement is the internal and external factors that support the change. External reinforcement includes the recognition, rewards, and celebration. Internal Reinforcement can come from feeling satisfied with the achievement (achievement) or other benefits derived from the change. Celebrating success and implement a recognition program

- Giving rewards to the highest value and comprehension ability test Iconix System

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- Collect feedback from employees
- Audit and performance measurement of the implementation of Iconix System

The results of the analysis Adkar models can be used to diagnose the resistance / refusal of members of the organization; help transition members of the organization through the change process; create a successful plan for personal and professional improvement as changes; and develop a change management plan for the members of KSC Beauty Clinic Jember.

Conclusion

Implementation approach Adkar in the implementation of software implementation Iconix System studied showed that most employees are aware of the importance of the program *Iconix System*, Generally motivated to get involved because of the element or another *lihak*, has intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, knowledge of the majority of employees are only subject to the ability of the program *Iconix System* conducted, and the results are implemented in the form of training on their own and work with others. Implementation of the Adkar approach still faces obstacles both from the human aspect, availability of facilities and the optimal time that disrupt learning achievement of the objectives of education programs *Iconix System*. However, efforts need to be done in order to improve the development of the implementation of the software implementation *Iconix System* at *KSCBeauty Clinic* muddy at a better future.

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